

Leak Detection and Localization in WSS: An ML-Based Framework for Timely Response

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ABSTRACT

Water losses represent one of the most persistent challenges for Water Supply Systems (WSS), with significant economic and environmental impacts, ranging from 3% to over 50% in WSS [1]. Leakage can occur in pipe and/or junctions due to uncontrolled actions such as pipe defects, excessive system pressure, or inadequate fitting, and often remain undetected for long periods of time [2, 3]. The Portuguese regulator ERSAR [4] reported in 2023 an average leakage of 5.5 m³/(km day) in the bulk side, representing a loss of more than 21 billion m³ per year. In the distribution size of the network, leakage was measured at 2.4 m³/(km day), equating to 4.6 billion m³ per year. Leakage management measures have been implemented to reduce these values, as observed in the gradual decrease compared with the previous years' data.

Leakage management measures include preventive measures, systematic assessment protocols, regulatory frameworks, control measures, detection and localization techniques, and repair initiatives [5]. The most critical step is leak detection and localization, where hardware- and software-based methods are the most common. These conventional leak detection techniques can be employed through integration with Digital Twins (DT) and Machine Learning (ML) models, enabling them to be a powerful tool for automated data analysis and hydraulic simulation [6], leading to substantial progress for a faster and more reliable leak detection and localization.

Therefore, this work presents a detection and localization framework for the early identification of water leaks in WSS using ML models, as shown in Figure 1. This framework includes two main parts: a hydraulic modelling module and a detection and localization module.

Figure 1. Proposed framework for detection and localization of water leaks.

The detection and localization module is the focus of this work, and its methodology is presented in Figure 2. It takes as input time series of pressure and flow measurements of the water network, and outputs a leak probability in order to improve the detection time. It integrates two main modules: (1) a ML-based regressor model, and (2) a mathematical anomaly classifier. The regressor model predicts the normal behaviour of the pressure time series and compares it with the measured values, to identify small deviations that may indicate a leak. After this, the mathematical anomaly classifier compares the reconstruction error to an adaptive threshold to classify new data samples. Additionally, an approximate leak localization probability is given based on which sensors most likely contribute to that anomaly.

Figure 2. Detection and Localization leak alarm.

The proposed framework was tested and validated using the data from the BattLeDIM benchmark case study [7], and different ML models, such as Neural Networks, Convolutional Neural Network, and Recurrent Neural Network, were tested showing promising results compared to the existing literature.

Overall, this framework enables faster leak detection in WSS by automatically identifying minor differences in values and helping operation teams to analysis the possible affected area, reducing the searching time and area.

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